

A PROGRESSIVE FAILURE MODEL FOR COMPOSITE LAMINATES INCLUDING MATRIX CRACKS INTERNAL TRACTION

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ABSTRACT

This paper concerns the shear modulus reduction due to transverse cracks and the evolution of transverse and shear damage. The effect of crack closure in axial and transverse response of the laminates has been already incorporated in damage models while in the shear direction it is still a challenge. Experimental investigation was done to measure the shear modulus reduction. The comparison of existing models with experimental data showed that shear damage is currently not suitably described. Accordingly, a shear damage evolution model was proposed that included the effect of internal tractions and crack closure on the shear modulus.

The damage model was derived using the thermodynamics of irreversible damage in a polymer composite. The current damage model is based on independent orthogonal damage orientations coinciding with the lamina material directions. Damage in the shear direction was defined as functions of the independent damage variables. We assumed, therefore, that transverse matrix cracks influence the transverse and shear response, regardless of how the transverse damage was induced. Since this work only considers matrix cracks, shear damage was defined as a function of transverse damage which simplifies the formulation for this demonstrative application. The constitutive law of this damage model is based on the complementary free energy density and the second law of the thermodynamics.

The model was implemented in Abaqus using a UMAT subroutine. The crack band theory was included in the model to eliminate the mesh dependency of the model. The numerical predictions of the modified shear damage model showed good agreement with experiment including saturation crack density, axial response and shear response.

1 INTRODUCTION

Laminate progressive failure models depend on a failure criterion for the first ply failure and a material degradation model to describe hardening or softening after first ply failure. Failure in the fiber direction is usually catastrophic, while degradation factors are applied when failure occurs in the matrix. The classical approach toward material degradation modeling in fiber reinforced composite materials describes material stiffness as a function of crack density. There are different analytical, semi-analytical and numerical models which focus on these solutions [1-2]. Another approach describes damage as a macroscopic state variable and defines material degradation in the framework of continuum damage mechanics [3]. In fiber reinforced composites, matrix damage can be described

as cracks either parallel or perpendicular to the fiber direction. Accordingly, a tensor can be used to represent damage with principal directions aligned with the material directions.

Transverse stiffness reduction has been widely studied, where agreement between models and experiment is common. By comparison, shear modulus softening from matrix cracks has received little attention, and tends not to agree with predictions. The available laminate damage models [4-11] assume a linear relation between transverse and in-plane shear damage without experimental evidence. According to the linear assumption, the matrix cracks parallel to the fiber direction have the same effect on the transverse and shear modulus. However the experimental investigations by Knops et al. [12] and later by Smith and Salvatian [13] showed that the shear modulus was less affected than the transverse modulus. These experimental observations were the motivation of the current study. This work focused on matrix cracks parallel to the fiber due to loading perpendicular to the fibers, (hereafter referred to transverse loading) and considered the effect of matrix cracks on transverse and shear damage evolution. The accuracy of the linear relation between shear and transverse damage was investigated in this study. The results were compared with existing models [4-11], which over predicted the observed in-plane shear modulus reduction.

2 CONTINUUM DAMAGE MODEL

From a practical point of view, a difficulty of the damage models for composite materials is the number of parameters needed to characterize their anisotropic behavior. To model the damage response of a fiber reinforced lamina, most continuum damage models define two independent damage variables according to the common failure modes in a lamina. In a fiber reinforced lamina d_1 represents damage in the fiber direction, whereas the d_2 represents damage in the matrix perpendicular to the fiber direction. When $d_i=0$ there is no damage or stiffness loss of the element while $d_i=1$ means total failure of the element and zero stiffness. Obviously, it is possible to define independent damage variables in the shear direction and also introduce independent variables for the interactions between damage modes. However, given the number of tests needed to define the unknown parameters, as the number of variables increases, the likelihood of experimental verification decreases.

The current proposed damage model is based on independent orthogonal damage orientations in a lamina coinciding with the material directions. Damage in the shear direction is defined as functions of the independent damage variables. We assume, therefore, that transverse matrix cracks influence the transverse and shear response, regardless of how the transverse damage was induced. Since this work only considered matrix cracks, shear damage was defined as a function of transverse damage which simplified the formulation for this demonstrative application. The formulation is in the local material coordinate system for each lamina. The constitutive law of the proposed damage model is based on the complementary free energy density and the second law of the thermodynamics. In this approach, it is assumed that there is a positive definite potential which is a function of free variables (the stresses) [15]. The potential function must enclose the origin and become zero at the origin with respect to the free variables [10]. The proposed form of the Gibbs energy is based on the works of Maimi et al. [10,11] and Lapczyk et al. [16] including the residual terms introduced by Chaboche and Maire [17] as

$$\begin{aligned} \phi = & \frac{1}{2E_1(1-d_1)} \sigma_{11}^2 \xi(\sigma_{11}) + \frac{1}{2E_1} \sigma_{11}^2 [1 - \xi(\sigma_{11})] + \frac{1}{2E_2(1-d_2)} \sigma_{22}^2 \xi(\sigma_{22}) \\ & + \frac{1}{2E_2} \sigma_{22}^2 [1 - \xi(\sigma_{22})] - \frac{\nu_{12} \sigma_{11} \sigma_{22}}{E_1} + \frac{(\sigma_{12} - \sigma_{12}^r)^2}{2G_{12}(1-d_2)} \xi(\sigma_{22}) \\ & + \frac{(\sigma_{12} - \sigma_{12}^r)^2}{2G_{12}(1-\beta d_2)} [1 - \xi(\sigma_{22})] + \phi^r(\sigma_{12}^r, d_2, \beta, \xi(\sigma_{22})) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where, ϕ^r is the residual energy density (defined below) and σ_{12}^r is the residual shear stress (which is takes the value 0 as an initial value). The step function $\xi(x)$ is defined as

$$\xi(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & x \leq 0 \\ 1, & x > 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

As will be discussed below, traction is observed to act across the crack faces under in-plane shear loading. This gives rise to a residual stress when a material with damage is loaded and loaded in shear. In compression, the proposed Gibbs energy function assumes no change in the transverse or axial stiffness, even in the presence of existing damage. (In general the proposed model can account for compression damage by defining damage variables for the compression energy density). It was assumed the in-plane shear modulus of the damaged material depended on the sign of the transverse stress. A material dependent parameter (β) described the sensitivity of the in-plane shear modulus of the damaged material to transverse stress. To simplify the formulation, and since the damage model and experimental investigation focused on matrix damage, shear damage was defined only as a function of transverse damage. The proposed approach can, nevertheless, describe shear damage as a function of fiber damage or any other independent damage mode. The strain tensor was derived using the proposed complementary free energy density function as

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \sigma} = S : \sigma \quad (3)$$

where S is the material compliance matrix.

2.1 Residual energy formulation

There are many continuum damage models based on damaged material response. However, only a few models can simultaneously simulate material anisotropy and the effect matrix crack closure on the lamina stiffnesses. The main challenge is introducing a material model which correlates with experimental evidence and satisfies the second law of thermodynamics. Chaboche and Maire [17] proposed a theory for dissipative behavior of ceramic matrix composites which considered crack closure effects and the corresponding energy function. They used a set of scalar damage variables and a fourth order damage tensor to describe the damage evolution in ceramic matrix composites. The same concept was adopted here using a second rank damage tensor. Chaboche and Maire [17] assumed an undamaged shear modulus due to crack closure, while the current model assumes reduction in shear modulus even when the cracks are closed but with a different rate compared with the open crack mode. In the shear direction, crack closure was modeled by introducing an extra term in the complementary free energy definition. Considering the energy density function, equation (1), and assuming initial transverse tension stress, the strain may be obtained from,

$$\varepsilon = S^+ : \sigma \quad (4)$$

where, S^+ is defined as

$$S^+ = \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \sigma \otimes \partial \sigma} \quad \text{where } \xi(\sigma_{22}) = 1 \quad (5)$$

Due to the activation of the residual shear stress, σ_{12}^r , if the sign of the transverse stress in the damaged element changes to compression, the formulation of the free energy is replaced by

$$\varepsilon = S^- : (\sigma - \sigma^r) \quad (6)$$

where S^- is defined as

$$S^- = \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial \sigma \otimes \partial \sigma} \quad \text{where } \xi(\sigma_{22}) = 0 \quad (7)$$

and the lamina residual stress, σ^r , is defined as

$$\sigma^r = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \sigma_{12}^r \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

The shear stress where crack closure occurred is denoted as $\sigma_{12} = \sigma_{12}^c$. The constitutive law (and accordingly stress strain curve) discontinuity is prevented by adding the residual stress and combining equations (4) and (6) as

$$\varepsilon^c = S^+ : \sigma^c = S^- : (\sigma^c - \sigma^r) \quad (9)$$

The residual stress may be rewritten as a function of crack closure stress σ^c as

$$\sigma^r = [I - (S^-)^{-1} : S^+] : \sigma^c \quad (10)$$

After crack closure, the residual elastic energy function is activated and the residual energy due to any further stress change is calculated. The complementary free energy evolution after the crack closure may be determined by integrating the equation (6) as;

$$\phi = \phi^c + \int_{\sigma^c}^{\sigma} \varepsilon(\sigma) d\sigma \quad (11)$$

where ϕ^c is the complementary free energy just at the crack closure and defined as $\phi^c = \frac{1}{2} \sigma^c : S^+ : \sigma^c$. Also, the complementary free energy evolution after crack closure may be determined using equation (1) as;

$$\phi = \frac{1}{2} (\sigma - \sigma^r) : S^- : (\sigma - \sigma^r) + \phi^r \quad (12)$$

Combining equations (11) and (12), the residual complementary free energy may be determined as

$$\phi^r = \frac{1}{2} \sigma^c : S^+ : \sigma^c - \frac{1}{2} (\sigma^c - \sigma^r) : S^- : (\sigma^c - \sigma^r) \quad (13)$$

where using equation (9), the residual complementary free energy may be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \phi^r &= \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^c : \sigma^r = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^c : [I - (S^-)^{-1} : S^+] : \sigma^c = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^c : [I - (S^-)^{-1} : S^+] : (S^+)^{-1} : \varepsilon^c \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^c : [(S^+)^{-1} - (S^-)^{-1}] : \varepsilon^c = \frac{1}{2} \sigma^r : [(S^+)^{-1} - (S^-)^{-1}]^{-1} : \sigma^r \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Using equation (10) and (14), the residual complementary free energy may be calculated and the value of residual stress is stored for each element. If the crack is closed at σ^c , the shear modulus changes and equation (14) describes the stored energy due to the induced residual stress. If the cracks open, due to transverse tension stress, the residual stress and the residual complementary free energy are released and take the value of zero. Considering equations (8) and (14), and using the compliance tensor in tension and compression, the residual complementary free energy was determined as

$$\phi^r(\sigma_{12}^r, d_2, \beta, \xi(\sigma_{22})) = -\frac{\sigma_{12}^r{}^2}{2G_{12}(1-\beta)d_2} (1 - \xi(\sigma_{22})) \quad (15)$$

According to the proposed model, the shear modulus is dependent on the crack opening mode. At the crack closure stress, $\sigma_{12} = \sigma_{12}^c$, equations (1) and (15) guarantee continuity in the shear stress strain response. If the cracks open ($\sigma_2 > 0$) at $\sigma_{12} = \sigma_{12}^c$, the stress-strain response is still continuous. If the cracks open when $\sigma_{12} \neq \sigma_{12}^c$ the shear stress-strain response is discontinuous since cracks will release stored energy like the process of inducing damage where the fracture energy releases.

This phenomenon is illustrated in Figure 1. Consider a material with damage loaded in shear while under transverse tension (line O-A in Figure 1). At point A the transverse stress changes to compression. If the shear stress is removed the material response would then follow line A-B in Figure 1 (i.e. closed cracks result in increased modulus). If the material is again loaded in shear while transverse compression is maintained, the material response would follow line A-B in Figure 1. If the transverse compression changes to transverse tension while shear is applied the stress-strain response jump to line O-A as the cracks open and the residual stress is removed.

Figure 1. Shear stress vs strain response due to crack closure effect

2.2 Energy dissipation

To satisfy the second law of thermodynamics, the rate of change of complementary free energy during the damage progression, $\dot{\phi}$ must be greater than the external applied work or

$$\dot{\phi} - \dot{\sigma} : \varepsilon \geq 0 \quad (16)$$

Rewriting equation (16) in terms of the defined damage variables results in

$$\left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \sigma} - \varepsilon \right) : \dot{\sigma} + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial d_1} \dot{d}_1 + \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial d_2} \dot{d}_2 \geq 0 \quad (17)$$

The stress rate tensor, $\dot{\sigma}$ can take any value depending on the boundary condition. By equation (3) the first term of equation (17) vanishes independent of the stress rate tensor. The thermodynamic forces in equation (17) are always positive as

$$\begin{aligned} Y_1 &= \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial d_1} = \frac{1}{2E_1(1-d_1)^2} \sigma_{11}^2 \geq 0 \\ Y_2 &= \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial d_2} = \frac{1}{2E_2(1-d_2)^2} \sigma_{22}^2 + \frac{(\sigma_{12} - \sigma_{12}^r)^2}{2G_{12}(1-d_2)^2} \xi(\sigma_{22}) \\ &+ \left[\frac{(\sigma_{12} - \sigma_{12}^r)^2}{2G_{12}(1-\beta d_2)^2} \beta + \frac{\sigma_{12}^{r^2}}{2G_{12}(1-\beta)d_2^2} \right] (1 - \xi(\sigma_{22})) \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Therefore, the positive evolution of the damage variables \dot{d}_1 and $\dot{d}_2 \geq 0$ (the Kuhn-Tucker condition) ensure the thermodynamically irreversibility of the model.

2.3 Failure criteria

A failure criterion describes the damage initiation point where the material stiffness should be degraded according to the damage model. The current continuum mechanics damage model is capable of implementing any failure criterion. For this study the Hashin and Rotem failure criterion for fiber reinforced lamina was chosen in which separate failure modes for fiber and matrix were defined under tension and compression stresses [18]. The Hashin and Rotem failure criterion may be written as

$$r_1 = \frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_1^+} \xi(\sigma_{11}) + \frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_1^-} [1 - \xi(\sigma_{11})] \quad (19)$$

$$r_2 = \left(\left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{X_2^+} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{X_{12}^-} \right)^2 \right) \xi(\sigma_{22}) + \left(\left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{X_2^-} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{X_{12}^+} \right)^2 \right) [1 - \xi(\sigma_{22})] \quad (20)$$

where, X_i^+ and X_i^- represent the tension and compression failure strength in direction “ i ”. If the value of r_i is equal or greater than one at any point, damage was introduced through the lamina. The parameter r_i was defined as the internal variable for the i^{th} damage mode, which takes an initial value of 1 when the material is intact and increases with damage growth.

2.4 Damage evolution

Damage evolution is a function that quantifies damage during the initiation and growth of damage through the material. There are several damage evolution functions in the literature using semi-empirical, thermodynamic or energy approaches. Matzenmiller et al. [9] and Maimi et al. [10] proposed a damage evolution law using an exponential function of the failure criterion and an empirical coefficient. Maimi et al. [10] proposed a more general function and included the crack band theory by Bazant [14] to ensure a correct computation of energy dissipation during the damage process. The exponential damage evolution law for each failure mode was defined as

$$d_i = 1 - \frac{1}{r_i} \exp[A_i\{1 - r_i\}] \quad (21)$$

where the term A_i is the damage law parameter which was based on crack band theory [14] which ensured the mesh independence of the model and adjusted the damage for each element according to the characteristic element length, L_c . For instance, in the case of fiber tension failure, the damage law parameter may be defined as

$$A_1 = \frac{2L_c X_1^{+2}}{2G_f E_1 - L_c X_1^{+2}} \quad (22)$$

where G_f is the fracture toughness associated with the fiber failure mode.

3 EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Salavatian and Smith [1-2] proposed an experimental method to measure material stiffness degradation due to matrix damage. A modified Iosipescu coupon was designed to study the evolution of shear and transverse damage. The proposed method showed good agreement with results from tubular specimens and has advantages of simplified specimen fabrication using standard test fixtures. The results provided the first experimental comparison of shear modulus reduction from transverse damage to predictive models. The coupon was designed to accommodate both axial and shear loading with controlled crack densities. A modified Iosipescu coupon with a $[0_1/90_7]_S$ layup was used. The characteristic V notches of the Iosipescu coupon were replaced with slots machined on both sides of the coupon. The notch height was selected to remove only the 90° plies as shown in Figure 2. The slotted region formed the coupon gage section where the desired crack density was introduced.

Figure 2. Slotted shear/tension coupon

Test coupons were fabricated from unidirectional S2-glass/epoxy pre-preg (Zentron DA 409U/S2) using hand lay-up and an autoclave cure at 250° F. The fiber volume of the cured laminate was 62%. Mechanical properties and strength of S2-glass/epoxy laminate were determined by standardized tests. The average values of the elastic stiffnesses are reported in Table 1. The strength and fracture energies are listed in Table 2; the fracture energies were taken from Maimi et al [11].

Table 1. Elastic property of S2-glass/epoxy

E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}
48.1	14.2	6.7	0.276

Table 2. Damage initiation properties of S2-glass/epoxy

Longitudinal tensile failure strain (%)	Transverse tensile failure strain (%)	In-plane shear failure strain (%)	fracture energy (fiber), G_f^I (N/mm)	fracture energy (matrix), G_m^I (N/mm)
0.024	0.0026	0.012	60	0.4

The slotted coupons were first subjected to an axial load to introduce transverse damage in the 90° plies. The numbers of cracks were counted using the Digital Image Correlation (DIC) spatial strain field and the load-displacement curve in situ. The load was stopped when the required number of cracks was achieved. To measure the transverse stiffness reduction from the transverse cracks, the axial test was repeated. The second axial test was done with a maximum load of 40% of the tensile strength to measure the elastic axial stiffness without inducing further damage. Coupons with crack densities from 0 up to 2.4 cracks/cm were prepared.

After the axial test, shear was applied using the Iosipescu fixture with a cross head speed of 0.5 mm/min. The displacement and strain of the coupons with pre-existing transverse damage were recorded using DIC and averaged over the gage section. The linear part of the shear stress–strain curve was used to determine the shear modulus.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Material degradation analysis

The results of the axial tension test showed material softening or damage in the slotted coupons as shown in Figure 3. The damage was primarily in the form of transverse cracks in the 90° plies. The loading curves of all the specimens nearly coincided while the slope of the reloading curves was proportional to the transverse crack density. The slope of the reloading curve was used to obtain the axial laminate stiffness reduction.

Two methods were used to describe damage. In the first method strain was averaged over the gage section as shown in Figure 2(hatched area). In this case the 90° lamina was defined as a representative element for which damage should be defined. In this approach, damage represents the whole gage section stiffness reduction. Damage was measured for the 90° plies by assuming there was no damage in the supporting 0° layers. To calculate d_2 and d_6 , the following procedure was applied for every test case. Damage from the axial load in the 90° plies, E_2 , was inferred from changes in E_x using lamination theory and assuming no damage in the 0° plies (damage occurs at a much lower strain in the 90° plies compared to the 0° plies). The shear modulus was found from the shear tests as done with the transverse damage, so that

$$d_2 = 1 - \frac{E_2}{E_2^0} \quad (23)$$

$$d_6 = 1 - \frac{G_{12}}{G_{12}^0} \quad (24)$$

where E_2^0 and G_{12}^0 were the undamaged transverse and shear moduli respectively.

Figure 3. The axial stress- strain curve of a 2.4 cracks/cm coupon and reloading curves for all test cases using constant gage area approach.

The current continuum damage models for fiber reinforced laminates assume the following relation between shear and transverse damage, independent of the cracks opening mode

$$(1 - d_6) = (1 - d_2) \quad (25)$$

According to the equation (25) there are no residual stress and energy terms in equation (1) and $\beta = 1$. The results of the experimental study were used to investigate the accuracy of this assumption, equation (25). Figure 4 compares the experimental values of d_2 and d_6 where less softening was observed in shear than in the transverse direction. Unlike the common assumption, equation (25), the same reduction for transverse and shear modulus was not observed.

Figure 4. Shear damage as a function of transverse damage. Boxes represent damage from strain over constant gage section area. Circles represent damage from strain over a variable gage

section area.

In the second approach DIC was used to overcome the experimental limitation of the transverse crack saturation. Instead of using specimens with different crack densities and a constant gage section area, the specimen with only one crack was used. Here, however, strain was averaged over $2l$ as shown in Figure 2. The variable l changed from 0.1mm to 12.5 mm. The lower bound of l was imposed by the step size and the image resolution of the DIC. The maximum value of l was the gage section from the first approach.

The variable gage area suggests a modified linear relation between d_2 and d_6 as shown in Figure 4 where the slope of the line is not equal to 1. Both uniform and variable gage area approaches show that shear damage evolution is different than equation (25). The variable gage section results indicate that even without a transverse compression stress the crack faces cannot slide freely. In shear, transverse crack surfaces are apparently sufficiently rough that relative motion is inhibited, yet sufficiently smooth that compliance is increased. According to this evidence, it was assumed the shear damage changes based on the crack opening mode. In case of an open crack mode under transverse tension, the common relation between shear and transverse damage, equation (25), was valid due to lack of internal traction over the crack faces. However, in case of transverse compression stress, (and even pure shear) a different shear damage law was applied by introducing the residual stress term and a new function as explained in equation (1). To determine the shear damage under the crack closure mode the material property β is needed. The results of the variable gage section method were used to suggest $\beta = 0.4$, as shown in Figure 4.

4.2 Numerical model

The constitutive models with different shear damage evolution laws were implemented in the Abaqus finite element package using a UMAT user subroutine, written in a Fortran compiler. The Abaqus nonlinear algorithm was based on a strain incremental formulation. The UMAT subroutine reports the trial stress and trial tangent stiffness matrix for each iteration according to the defined constitutive model. Damage variables evolve as internal state variables when the nonlinear algorithm converges for each increment [19].

Two different shear damage models were compared with experiment. The first model was the classical shear damage model for fiber reinforced composites, assuming equation (25) and using equation (1) where $\beta=1$ and no residual complementary free energy. With $\beta=1$ the crack closure mode has no effect on the shear response. The second model was the shear damage model assuming crack closure and internal traction effects and different damage laws for transverse tension and compression loading, (i.e. equation (1) with all terms included).

Figure 5. Damage induced in the 90 ° lamina at the end of loading step one due to axial tension

4.3 Comparison of the models

The shear damage functions were implemented in Abaqus and compared with the experimental

results of the slotted coupon. The finite element models of $[0/90_7]_s$ coupons were created. A symmetry plane was defined along length of the coupon so that half of the coupon was modeled. A plane stress element was used for the whole model. The mesh size continuously decreased toward the gage section. Three separate, continuous loading steps were defined in the same order as the experimental loading. During the first step, one side of the coupon was fixed and axial tension was applied to the other side until the required crack densities were reached. The number of cracks or the amount of induced damage can be seen by the elements with $d_i = 1$ as shown in Figure 5. Models were run to various axial load levels to achieve the desired crack density, as was done experimentally. Next, the boundary conditions of these models were changed to apply shear. The models (with damage) were then loaded in shear within the elastic range (i.e. without inducing additional damage) to measure the effect of damage on the shear modulus.

Figure 6. Comparison of the experimental axial stress- strain curve of a 2.4 cracks/cm coupon with simulation

Figure 6 compares the experimental axial tension stress- strain result with the numerical simulation. Both models showed the same result for the first step. During step one, damage initiation was triggered by transverse failure in the 90° plies and the overall response of the specimen was dominated by transverse stiffness reduction. Since both models have the same transverse damage evolution law, the first step response was the same regardless of the shear damage model.

The experimental transverse crack saturation for the gage section was 2.4 cracks/cm. The numerical simulation showed the same crack density saturation. After reaching the saturated crack density in the gage section area the next crack happened outside the slotted region, similar to experiment. As a reminder, this is a continuum damage model which means there is no crack or discontinuity in the model; however the line of elements with $d_2=1$ were considered as one crack through the thickness.

The shear modulus reductions for various crack densities were simulated using the following approaches: a classical approach assuming a linear relation between shear and transverse damage without the crack closure effect; and transverse damage without a crack closure effect and shear damage including internal traction and crack closure effects. Figure 7, compares the experimental data of the shear modulus reduction with the numerical results. The comparison showed that the classical linear shear damage model overestimates the shear modulus reduction, particularly at higher crack densities.

The result of classical linear model showed ignoring the crack closure effect with the traction free assumption cannot adequately describe shear damage in fiber reinforced laminates. Equation (1) considered the internal traction for a fully damaged element by using different damage laws when the cracks are open and closed. The result of the proposed damage model, equation (1) is included in

Figure 10 and indicates good agreement with the observed shear modulus degradation over all the crack densities considered.

Figure 10. Experimental shear modulus reduction [1] compared with proposed damage model, equation (1), classical damage model, equation (1) without crack closer & internal traction effects.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The common assumption between shear and transverse damage, independent of the cracks closure mode was investigated. Transverse damage was introduced to the specimens after which they were loaded using a modified Iosipescu shear fixture. The experimental results showed common assumption does not sufficiently describe shear response. A modified shear damage model was proposed. The proposed model includes traction at the internal cracks under pure shear or shear-transverse compression loading. Under shear-transverse tension it was assumed the crack is opened and the shear load cannot transfer through the damage area. A residual energy term was defined which stores the change in the elastic energy due to crack closure and material stiffness increase. The residual energy can be released if the stress state returns to the same stress state at which the crack closed or if the cracks open. Experimental results showed the proposed model correctly predicts the shear response and accounts for the effects of transverse loading.

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